

INTERNATIONAL HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN

Abdullabekova Noilaxon G'ofurjon qizi

Namangan State University

2nd-level student of hotel management and organization

Abstract: *In this article, using the hotel business in Uzbekistan and foreign experience in this field, suggestions and recommendations are presented regarding the improvement and development of the hotel business, the development of hotels and hotel chains in Uzbekistan.*

Keywords: *international hotels, hotel chain, PEST analysis, foreign experience, tourism, tourist.*

Introduction: Uzbekistan is known to the world for its wonderful nature, historical cities, hospitality, national cuisine, and is causing an increase in the flow of tourists. The increase in the flow of tourists contributes to the development of the hotel business in Uzbekistan. Hotel business is directly related to tourism. Tourism is a profitable and highly profitable industry, which plays an important role in the formation of the gross domestic product, in increasing the foreign trade balance, and in providing employment to the population. Hotel business is a business network that provides services to various types of guests based on the principle of hospitality. The development of the hotel business directly leads to the development of other sectors, for example, transport, trade, construction, agriculture, production of consumer goods, service sector.

The role of international hotel chains is undoubtedly very important for tourism, as well as for other sectors and the economy as a whole. The hotel industry is one of the largest economic sectors in the world. International hotel

for the economic analysis of the business, it is important to determine its role in the country's economy.

The impact of the hotel industry on the country's economy can be considered as a result of the spending of tourists on the purchase of hotel services. Expenditure by foreign tourists in the country increases the cost of hotel components.

There are a few hotels in Uzbekistan that meet international requirements and standards. In order to meet the demands of the global hotel industry, a hotel needs to have everything from facilities, utilities to staff to perfection. In international practice, hotels are divided into three levels of service: world standard, medium level and limited services.

1. World class service. In accordance with international standards, hotels serve the elite of society - high-ranking politicians, representatives of world-famous science and culture, heads of large enterprises and other wealthy customers. Material base and highly qualified service personnel should be prepared for these hotels. In the hotel rooms, guests can see all the conditions corresponding to 4- and 5-star hotels according to world standards. The interior of the building is luxuriously decorated [13-19]. Guests are served by several restaurants, bars and cafes. International level hotels pay special attention to each guest and include a large number of service staff. This allows to provide various services and quickly respond to the requests of guests.

2. Average level of service. Hotels with this level cover the largest segment of hotel service consumers. The level of services offered at the hotel is simple but adequate. Additional services are almost never provided [20-25]. These hotels have restaurants, cafes, lounges for hotel residents and other guests. Businessmen, travelers and family travelers usually live in such hotels. Hotels of this level have a system of discounts for regular customers, groups and families. Discounts are also available for students, city residents, large visiting groups, and more.

3. Limited Service. Hotels with a limited set of services are a rapidly growing segment of the hotel business market. These hotels focus on providing guests with clean, comfortable yet affordable rooms and catering to the most basic needs. Such hotels are used by travelers who are not rich. These can be children, tourist groups, people on vacation, retirees, small businessmen, etc.

Chain hotels belonging to the brands of Western countries apply service standards that are well known to their customers and have been developed over the years. No matter where the hotel is located in Russia, India, Spain or Great Britain, its guests always choose the service that meets their requirements.

According to the World Tourism Organization, there are 16 million hotels in the world, and 20% of them are hotel chains. Hotel chains are still new to the hotel industry, which has a long history. The first hotel chains appeared in the USA in the late 1930s. Since then, the United States has been the leader in the number of hotels owned by a given hotel chain. About 70% of hotels in the US are chain hotels. Among them, we can include large hotel chains such as JW Marriott, Hilton, Sheraton, Intercontinental. Currently, hotel chains are firmly established in the services market. Hotels belonging to hotel chains are constantly operating in major cities of the world.

A number of laws and decisions on the development of tourism are being developed in Uzbekistan. In particular, the "Concept for the development of tourism in the Republic of Uzbekistan in 2019-2025" was developed. According to the concept:

- improvement of the legal framework in the field of tourism activity;
- implementation of international norms and standards aimed at creating favorable conditions for the development of tourism;
- development of tourism infrastructure and creation of an acceptable and comfortable tourism environment;
- development of transport logistics;

- expansion of internal and external directions;
- improving the quality of transport services;
- diversification of tourism products and services aimed at different segments of the tourism market;
- Development of domestic tourism, which provides stimulation of the activity of tourism activity subjects aimed at meeting the need for tourism services within the republic;
- Promotion of tourism products of the Republic of Uzbekistan in international and domestic tourism markets;
- strengthening the image of the country as safe for travel and recreation;
- improvement of the system of personnel training, retraining and advanced training for the tourism industry;

The work done to make tourism one of the strategic sectors of the economy in Uzbekistan was reflected in various ratings and nominations. In particular, in recent years, Uzbekistan has been named the world's best tourist destination by The Guardian, the fastest developing country by Wanderlust, and the best developing country by Grandvoyage. In addition, the World Tourism Organization under the UN has rated Uzbekistan as 4th in the list of rapidly developing countries in the field of tourism.

Analysis and results: The analysis of international experience shows that when hotels are combined in a chain, the profitability of one room is 7 times higher than in independent hotels. These chains continue to thrive even as employment levels have steadily declined in many regions in recent years. % of business travelers and 2/3 of leisure travelers choose a hotel by brand. International experience allows us to define the most important single hotel standards for the formation of an international network of hotels:

- financial standards
- operational standards

- personnel management standards
- sales and marketing standards
- facility requirements standards

International hotel chains, enterprises located abroad, often demonstrate their superiority over national companies by using innovative, new and advanced technologies. The latter increases managerial and entrepreneurial experience and competitiveness. Countries such as Thailand and Tunisia are taking advantage of international experiences in the field of hospitality, and revenues are growing in local hospitality businesses. The development of the international hotel business will certainly increase the efficiency of the national economy. The international hotel network has a double economic impact on the national economy.

Satisfying consumer demands by expanding and improving existing capabilities will lead to an increase in the quality level and an increase in the qualifications of service providers. Scientific research is being conducted in the world aimed at fully using the potential of tourism. These are to ensure the development of the tourism industry, to increase the efficiency and quality of tourist services, to ensure that the services provided in hotels meet international standards.

Economists also offer a number of analyzes in the development of the hotel business. SWOT analysis, PEST analysis, etc. One of the methods that help to develop the hotel business in Uzbekistan is PEST analysis. It is known that PEST is composed of the following English words:

1. Political - political
2. Economic - economic
3. Social - social
4. Technological - technological

Political factors are important in doing business. In order to create a hotel business development strategy, it is necessary to pay attention to the following political factors:

- political situation in the country;
- level of state influence on business and industry;
- level of corruption in the industry;
- existence of administrative barriers;
- the biggest political changes in the last 5 years;
- State support of entrepreneurship. Economic factors also influence the development of the sector:
- growth rates of the country's economy and industry;
- interest rates for loans;
- exchange rate;
- inflation rate and real income of the population;
- investment and taxes;
- the biggest changes in the economy in the next 5 years.

Socio-demographic factors. It is necessary to study the social factor in the business development strategy:

- the population;
- level of recreation of the population;
- cultural environment, values.

Technological factors. Scientific and technological achievements are of great importance in the development of any business. The analysis of technological factors includes the study of the following components.

- contribution to market development of technologies;
- new information technologies; opportunities for automation, certain procedures, or robotization of workplaces;
- use and development of internet and mobile devices;
- standards of new equipment used by the hotel;

Of course, hotel activities in Uzbekistan are focused not only on the domestic market, but also on the foreign market. Therefore, for the development of the

industry, it is necessary to select and analyze the above-mentioned factors, as well as the main factors that contribute to and influence the development of the business. Obviously, a single analysis will not be enough to develop a complete strategy for the restaurant business. Along with the PEST analysis, it is advisable to conduct a SWOT analysis. Because, if we take into account the strengths and weaknesses, threats and existing opportunities in the hotel business through SWOT analysis, and use the above-mentioned international experiences, I think that the hotel business will be the most prosperous and profitable industry in Uzbekistan.

Reference:

Алиев, А., & Мусаева, М. З. К. (2021). СИСТЕМЫ ЗАЩИТЫ БИОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ДАННЫХ. *Academic research in educational sciences*, 2(4), 393-396.

Aliyev, A. A. (2021). СИСТЕМЫ ЗАЩИТЫ БИОМЕТРИЧЕСКИХ ДАННЫХ. *Scienceweb academic papers collection*.

Исмоилов Ш. М., Абдужалилов С., Алиев А. КЎНДАЛАНГ КЕСИМИ ИХТИЁРИЙ БЎЛГАН СТЕРЖЕНЛАРНИНГ ГЕОМЕТРИК ВА МЕХАНИК ПАРАМЕТРЛАРИНИ АНИҚЛАШ АЛГОРИТМИ //Results of National Scientific Research. – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 4. – С. 49-56.

Ayubjon o'gli, A. A. (2022). MOLIYAVIY TEXNOLOGIYALAR HAQIDA TUSHUNCHASI VA UALRNING TURLARI. *Academic Research*, 1(4), 64-69.

Ayubjon o'gli A. A. PRINCIPLES OF FINANCIAL INNOVATION //Academic Research. – 2022. - Jild 1. – №. 4. - S. 70-73.

Ayubjon o'g'li A. A., Islomjon I. AXBORT TIZIMLARINING DASTURIY TAMINOTI BANK SOHASIDAGI AHAMIYATI //INTERNATIONAL SCIENTIFIC AND PRACTICAL CONFERENCE" THE TIME OF SCIENTIFIC PROGRESS". – 2022. – Т. 1. – №. 1. – С. 67-73.

Ibrohimjon o'g'li I. I., Ayubjon o'g'li A. A. LOYIXALARNI BOSHQARISHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA AXBOROT XAVFSIZLIGIDA

